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MODERATE AND ULTRA-HYPOFRACTIONATION: NEW STANDARDS

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A recent systemic review of 17 randomized trial involving more than 10,000 patients confirmed the benefit of adjuvant radiotherapy (RT) on local control and overall survival for women with early breast cancer (BC). Shortened, hypofractionated radiotherapy (Hypo-RT) schedules were compared to standard fractionation in many randomized trials with a follow-up of 5–12 years. The results using moderate Hypo-RT were the first studies showing equivalence vs conventional RT in terms of local control, survival, and toxicity. Thus, the recent update of the American Society of Radiation Oncology evidence-based guidelines on RT for the whole breast confirmed that hypo-RT represents the new standard for patients with early-stage BC, regardless of age, chemotherapy administration, and breast size.

More recently, a new level in Hypo-RT has been crossed. The first high-quality clinical trial to support ultra-hypofractionated RT (Ultra-Hypo-RT) to the whole breast for invasive early-stage breast cancer has been published in April 2020, coinciding with the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Adoption of Ultra-Hypo-RT has increased substantially after the publication and used preferentially in patients with lower risk disease, suggesting careful selection for this new approach while long-term data are maturing.

These results led ESTRO Advisory committee of radiation oncology practice to state that moderately hypofractionated radiotherapy can be offered to any patient for whole breast, chest wall (with or without reconstruction), and nodal volumes. Ultra-Hypo-RT can also be offered for non-nodal breast or chest wall (without reconstruction) indication of RT either as standard of care or within a randomized trial or prospective cohort.

In my presentation I will discuss both data of moderate and severe Hypo-RT in patients with or without the need for regional nodal irradiation.

Keywords: early breast cancer, radiotherapy, ultra-hypo-RT

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